

IMPORTANT ASPECTS SPECIFIC TO THE IMPROVEMENT OF MECHANISMS OF PEACE AND STABILITY IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF NEW UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract: In this article, the development of the social development of New Uzbekistan and the processes of consolidation of peace and stability, of course, have a unique partnership with the neighboring countries. For example, the formation of security, stability, harmonious neighborhood environment in the vicinity of Uzbekistan has been established as a priority task in the near future. The relations between the countries of the region are expressed by the fact that the relations between the border regions of neighboring countries are expanding, and the mechanisms of public diplomacy are being actively used.

Key words: peace, security, globalization, economic, social, political, cultural and ideological, social development, social structure, stability, national idea, cultural heritage, history of statehood, science, innovation, intellectual work, unified history.

INTRODUCTION

Improving the mechanisms of peace and stability in the social development of new Uzbekistan is of unique strategic importance, and today the most important issue that occupies the center of attention of the world community and all mankind is peace and security, more precisely, the issue of ensuring peace, security and stability in the whole world. In the current period, the development of societies cannot be imagined without the influence of globalization processes on people's mentality, spiritual world, and social behavior.

The ways of further development of a person in the conditions of globalization depend on the social consciousness of a person, guiding goals, values, life concepts, worldview and, finally, what changes are taking place in his relations with society. Therefore, in the social and humanitarian sciences, great attention is being paid to the impact of globalization not only on the economic, social, political, but also on the cultural and ideological spheres of society. Processes show that the concept of a world without boundaries, where territories and distances lose their original meaning, is gaining a real shape, thinking about the "global village" (global village), "networked society" (networked society) and defining a qualitatively new level of the speed of this process. a new term for "hyper globalization" is applied to all aspects, such as: reflects the increasing speed of international relations in the fields of economy, information, finance, people, goods, money, and movement of ideas. It is therefore important that all countries act in unison to strengthen peace and stability in the current situation, because any local conflict can turn into a global thermonuclear war, if any kind of breach of peace is a threat to the general peace. "A public decision-making system based on openness and justice and serving the interests of people has been formed in the management of the state and society. Most importantly, we have changed the principle of "state-society-man" which has been in effect for many years.

The development of the social development of the new Uzbekistan and the processes of consolidation of peace and stability, of course, have a unique partnership with the neighboring countries. For example, the formation of security, stability, harmonious neighborhood environment in the vicinity of Uzbekistan has been established as a priority task in the near future. As time progresses towards development, modern innovative technologies, which are the impetus and means for this process, will not fail to develop. In today's information world, information sharing, information ownership and information security are the most important issues. In modern times, the concepts of sustainable development and security cannot be imagined separately. The fact that relations between neighboring countries are expanding at the level of the border regions, and the mechanisms of public diplomacy are being actively used are enriching the relations of the countries of the region. Special emphasis is placed on expanding cooperation between legislative bodies, and inter-parliamentary friendship groups are being formed. Stability and security are the decisive factors of the development of every country, the investment attractiveness of its economy.

The development of any nation depends on the attitude of the youth layer of the society to the national ideas and values, how it affects the minds of the youth and how they rely on their practical activities. Young people make up more than half of the population of our republic. It will also be related to the understanding of the national idea, confidence and faith of young people, what new values are formed. Because the national idea, first of all, looks at the youth as its object, and secondly, the youth are considered to be the advanced developers of the national idea and pass it on to the next generation. The more the youth are armed with the national idea and understand it, the more progress the society will make. This situation determines the relationship between the national idea and the youth. In other words, the more meaningful the national idea is, the more it serves to determine the long-term goals and interests of everyone, and ultimately the nation's perspective, the faster the youth will accept it and form their own positive attitude towards it. Therefore, the society will have ideologically trained, patriotic, modern knowledge youth according to the ideas and thoughts that the society offers to the youth through the national ideology.

Young people belong to such a social group of society that they have a sharp emotional intelligence and are more aware of situations of disparity between words and practice. Certain "injustices" common to adults can seriously damage the mind and outlook of young people, which are not yet fully formed. Therefore, spiritual and spiritual conditions related to the national idea, national pride and honor are important among young people. The significance of the national idea for mobilizing, inspiring, and inviting young people to a great future, its place and role in education and training is determined depending on how appropriate and compatible it is with the realities of life, real existence, and people's life.

Ideological education is also very important in the formation of the national. Ideological education is a process aimed at forming the worldview of a person, social group, nation, society, arming them with ideological knowledge that expresses certain goals. If the ideas are fair and true, if they correspond to the needs of the majority, if the means of education in this field are effective, and if the teachers are active and selfless, then the intended goal of ideological education will be achieved. In cases where society and the people have not yet realized their interests, formed their own ideology, and mobilized towards their goals, the possibility of being influenced by foreign and harmful ideas increases. This makes it an urgent task to establish ideological education, to constantly inculcate the principles of healthy

ideology into the hearts and minds of the population. Ideological education in society requires the joint activity of the family, pre-school children's institutions, schools, lyceums, colleges, higher educational institutions, mass media, public organizations. The continuing education system is the main link of ideological education, because the task of instilling ideological goals into the minds of young people is mainly carried out through education. The cultural heritage of the people, national values, exemplary lives of great thinkers are important in the formation of national pride and honor.

Young Generation" Karimov I.A. High spirituality is an indomitable work of instilling the ideas of social justice of the national independence ideology into the minds of young people through Abu Nasr Farabi's "City of Virtuous People", Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig", Nizammulk's "Politics", Amur Temur's "Tuzuklar", Alisher Navoi's "Mahbub ul- "Qulub" famous works serve as a historical-scientific source.

Because "the great country of the future must first of all take care of the culture, education and spirituality of future citizens. As we leave a free and prosperous Motherland to the young generation, as we intend for them to continue the great works of our thinkers and state leaders, we should pay attention to the spiritual awakening of the youth. The time has come to wake up from the sleep of heedlessness and look to the future with bright eyes. Now young people have started to realize their identity. Along with feeling the kind of land we live in, striving for universal values, Eastern philosophy, the light of Uzbek thinking began to take place on everyone's lips. The principle of restoration and development of our national traditions and customs has strengthened.

Appreciation of our Islamic religion has led to filling our spirituality with new meanings. We began to inherit the cultural treasure of our great grandfathers. We had the opportunity to be proud of them. Conditions have been created for peaceful living of representatives of all nationalities and peoples living in our country.

The new Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which guarantees human freedom and liberty, was adopted. "Uzbekistan's global community, first of all, should strengthen and develop friendly relations with neighboring countries on the basis of cooperation, mutual support, peace and harmony." It consists of moral, ethical and cultural development of the society, spiritual values, national idea, cultural heritage, history of the Uzbek people and statehood, as well as ensuring continuity and continuity of education, as well as raising a mature generation.

Man is a creature that always creates new forms. In order to directly express his feelings, he uses the language tool or the methods accepted by the society. We cannot communicate our feelings to each other without putting them in a certain form.

The forms we create are constantly changing - this is influenced by traditions, changes in the spirit of the times. In fact, things that are unchangeable seem to us to have no trace of vitality, and we change them.

The increasing conflict of different interests in the international arena, the intensifying problems in world politics and economy, and the increasing number of advocates of changing the general picture of the world are manifested as the most important characteristics of the current global world development. In the analysis of such complex universal processes, it is possible and necessary to approach on the basis of various criteria. Threats to security and stability today are not in the form of a specific large-scale armed conflict, but in the form of

negative, degenerate consequences of events affecting military-political, economic, environmental and human resources.

There are many honorable tasks in the world, but the most honorable among them is to protect the holy Motherland. Our hearts are filled with feelings of pride and pride from the great achievements of our national army in a short period of time. The brave, brave and loyal military personnel of our Motherland find their comfort in selflessness. For them, there is no happiness greater than the happiness of their people - happiness, well-being, peace and prosperity of their country. The idea of development of the homeland is a creative idea that combines the sense of belonging to the homeland, the interests of each person with the interests of the country, and encourages him to serve the people's happiness. It represents the highest goal of national independence - the realization of the dreams and hopes of all citizens living in Uzbekistan related to the development of the country. Honoring, honoring and serving the motherland is enshrined in Article 52 of our Constitution. For example, "Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the duty of every citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan." Citizens are obliged to perform military or alternative service in accordance with the law."

Military patriotism in young people is a feeling that shows high morality, and its content is strengthened by direct and indirect responsibility for the protection of the Motherland, its security and integrity. That's why true military patriotism requires putting the family above the family, the Motherland above the Motherland, and humanity above the Motherland. The important point is that the feelings in it do not fit into the narrow circle of patriotism, they "go beyond" it. Military patriotism is not limited to loving or loving the Motherland, but is manifested in mobilizing all the strength and intelligence to solve problems related to the protection of the Motherland.

In this regard, as President Shavkat Mirziyoev stated in his speech on January 10, 2018 at the Security Council meeting on the topic "Our armed forces are a strong guarantee of the stability and development of our country": "...we have identified the strengthening of the defense potential of our country as one of the priorities of the Action Strategy for the Development of Uzbekistan. According to the strategy, in 2017, among other areas, large-scale changes were made in military construction. In a short period of time, we achieved the first concrete results and developed a strategic approach to our renewed Armed Forces", and the reforms, renewal and changes implemented in our national army are pleasing to everyone living in this country - young and old alike.

Decisions made by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoev regarding the military sector, the benefits and favorable conditions created for military personnel, the provision of long-term preferential mortgage loans for providing them with housing, the provision of long-term preferential mortgage loans to young people undergoing military service in higher educational institutions By widely explaining and promoting opportunities such as giving preferential passes among the population, especially young people, several works are being carried out by the state to make young people interested in becoming a military profession, to strengthen the defense potential of our country, and to preserve peace in our country. To educate students and pupils in the spirit of military patriotism by widely promoting the content and essence of the large-scale work that is being carried out. allows to educate in the spirit. In addition, in military units and educational institutions, in order to further increase the interest of young people in

the military profession, to develop patriotic qualities, historical heroes Tomaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Babur Mirza, who are the symbols of patriotism from our great ancestors, and the life and work, bravery, military organization of meetings and roundtables expressing their tactics and promoting their patriotism will give a great positive result.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the social development of the new Uzbekistan will be fully embodied in the psyche of the people due to the formation of important aspects unique to the social development of the new Uzbekistan, interethnic harmony and solidarity, and being based on the universal basis.

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